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1. Changes with respect to the description of work

No changes compared to the description of the task.

2. Dissemination and uptake

Presentation of the core concepts of carbon debt and the work pertaining to feasibility during various stakeholder workshops and high-level meetings such as COPs and SBSTAs. For a full list, please refer to Annex I.

3. Short summary of results (<250 words)

Achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement requires more than emissions reductions—it demands a balance between ambition, feasibility, and fairness. This report explores the international cooperation and support necessary to advance fairness across regions, structured around three interrelated dimensions: governance capacity, interregional equity, and intergenerational equity.

Drawing on scenarios from the ENGAGE project, we show that incorporating feasibility reshapes the timing and distribution of regional mitigation efforts. OECD90+ and China+ regions are projected to reach net-zero emissions earlier, aligned with current pledges and stronger institutional capacity, compared to default scenarios without any feasibility considerations. In contrast, the Rest of the World (RoW) will require substantial international support to enhance ambition and action. This includes deeper near-term mitigation in high-capacity regions, as well as expanded mechanisms for technology transfer, institutional capacity-building, and climate finance.

We find that scenarios with more ambitious mitigation in regions with high institutional capacity still fall short of equity benchmarks such as historical responsibility. To address this, we introduce the concept of net-zero carbon debt—a transparent metric for quantifying excess emissions and drawdown obligations, offering additional guidance for climate finance and fair-share assessments.

Achieving ambitious climate targets in a way that balances feasibility and fairness will require coordinated global action. This includes deep domestic emissions reductions in high-capacity regions, alongside significantly scaled-up support for lower-income countries—particularly in areas such as clean energy, infrastructure, and governance. Equally critical is the large-scale mobilization of climate finance, ensuring it is more closely aligned with principles of equity. The newly launched Justice Model Intercomparison Project (JustMIP) will further explore how various dimensions of justice influence global mitigation pathways and the resulting demands for international cooperation.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

Pelz, S., Ganti, G., Lamboll, R., Grant, L., Smith, C., Pachauri, S., Rogelj, J., Riahi, K., Thiery, W., & Gidden, M. J. (2025). Using net-zero carbon debt to track climate

overshoot responsibility. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 122(13), e2409316122. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2409316122>

Brutschin, E., Bertram, C., Baptista, L. B., Bosetti, V., Daioglou, V., de Boer, H.-S., Drouet, L., Fosse, F., Fragkiadakis, D., Fragkiadakis, K., Fricko, O., Fujimori, S., Kejun, J., Krey, V., Kikstra, J., Pianta, S., Pelz, S., Riahi, K., Richters, O., Rodrigues, R., Schaeffer, R., Scheifinger, K., Silva, D., Tagomori, I., van Ruijven, B., van Vuuren, D., & Vrontisi, Z. (Revise and Resubmit). *Aligning differentiated ambition with the Paris Agreement goals*. Manuscript under review, *Environmental Research: Climate*.

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1. Introduction

Delivering on the Paris Agreement requires not only ambitious mitigation, but also a globally fair distribution of effort and responsibility. As climate action accelerates, the challenge lies in ensuring that pathways to net-zero emissions reflect both the capabilities and responsibilities of different regions and generations. This report focuses on the international cooperation and support required to advance fairness, structured around three interrelated dimensions: governance capacity, interregional equity, and intergenerational equity.

To explore these dimensions, we combine global Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) with new conceptual and methodological tools – incorporating diverse justice considerations and assessments of governance capacity – and examine how these can be directly integrated into the models. The goal is to understand how different justice and feasibility elements interact and to draw implications for both scenario development and international cooperation. The report is organized into two core analytical sections, followed by a discussion that synthesizes the findings.

Section 2: Governance Capacity examines how institutional capacity to implement policies affects the implementation of mitigation pathways. Scenarios that account for feasibility constraints are used to assess how regions with high institutional capacity might increase their ambition to hedge against the risk that regions with limited capacity may be unable to implement similarly ambitious climate policies. The section also explores in more detail the forms of international support – such as enhanced near-term targets in high-capacity regions—that may be necessary to close feasibility gaps in a fair and effective manner.

Section 3: Net-Zero Carbon Debt introduces a formalized approach to assessing fairness via the concept of Net-Zero Carbon Debt, which quantifies the gap between a region’s actual emissions trajectory and its fair share of the global carbon budget. When implemented in IAMs, these metrics can offer a transparent and interoperable foundation for evaluating equity outcomes and identifying needs for international cooperation. The framework also provides insights into how carbon debt can inform climate finance, technology transfer, and the evolution of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs).

Section 4: Ambition through Justice and Societal Considerations synthesizes these findings considering growing calls to more meaningfully integrate societal and justice-related dimensions into quantitative scenario modeling.

Together, these approaches and tools provide a pathway to expand the current scenario space by integrating critical feasibility and justice perspectives into future modeling efforts, while also illuminating the associated requirements for international cooperation.

2. Governance Capacity

The scenarios that we refer to in this section were developed for the following study:

Bertram, C., Brutschin, E., Drouet, L., Luderer, G., van Ruijven, B., Reis, L. A., Baptista, L. B., de Boer, H.-S., Cui, R., Daioglou, V., Fosse, F., Fragkiadakis, D., Fricko, O., Fujimori, S., Hultman, N., Iyer, G., Keramidas, K., Krey, V., Kriegler, E., ... Riahi, K. (2024). Feasibility of peak temperature targets in light of institutional constraints. *Nature Climate Change*, 14, 954–960. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-024-01908-6>

Summary of the insights from:

Brutschin, E., Bertram, C., Baptista, L. B., Bosetti, V., Daioglou, V., de Boer, H.-S., Drouet, L., Fosse, F., Fragkiadakis, D., Fragkiadakis, K., Fricko, O., Fujimori, S., Kejun, J., Krey, V., Kikstra, J., Pianta, S., Pelz, S., Riahi, K., Richters, O., Rodrigues, R., Schaeffer, R., Scheifinger, K., Silva, D., Tagomori, I., van Ruijven, B., van Vuuren, D., & Vrontisi, Z. (under review). *Aligning differentiated ambition with the Paris Agreement goals*. Manuscript under review, *Environmental Research: Climate*.

In this section, we build on the work of the ENGAGE project, which developed a new generation of global mitigation scenarios that explicitly incorporate feasibility constraints into Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs). These constraints focus both on specific technologies (e.g., strict limitations on the scale-up of geological carbon storage) and on broader structural factors, such as varying levels of regional institutional capacity.

A growing body of ex-post evaluations has benchmarked climate mitigation scenarios against real-world trends and alternative lines of evidence (Brutschin et al., 2021; Warszawski et al., 2021; Wilson et al., 2013, 2021), highlighting persistent feasibility gaps in existing scenario ensembles. In response, Bertram et al. (2024) as part of the ENGAGE project introduced a new suite of global scenarios that integrate technological and institutional feasibility constraints directly into the scenario design process.

The emphasis on institutional capacity in this set of scenarios is grounded in political economy research, which has shown that institutions are central to explaining cross-country differences in the provision of public goods (Acemoglu et al., 2002; Rodrik et al., 2004). This insight is particularly salient in the context of climate policy, where growing empirical evidence shows that countries with stronger institutional capacity tend to implement higher carbon taxes (Levi et al., 2020), have more effective regulatory environments (Creutzig et al., 2023; Eskander & Fankhauser, 2020; von Dulong & Hagen, 2024), and make more credible climate commitments (Victor et al., 2022). Similarly, countries with robust institutions are more likely to pursue ambitious coal phase-out plans (Jewell et al., 2019), achieve greater reductions in CO₂ emissions (Ronaghi et al., 2020), and expand renewable energy consumption (Uzar, 2020).

Among the many potential indicators of institutional capacity (Cingolani, 2013; Hanson & Sigman, 2021; Savoia & Sen, 2015), the ENGAGE scenarios adopt the “government effectiveness” metric from the World Bank (Kaufmann et al., 2010) to differentiate carbon prices across the considered regions or to constrain the respective regional CO₂ FFI emissions (Bertram et al., 2024). This indicator measures the quality of public service delivery, policy formulation, and implementation capacity of national governments. It has been projected for all countries to 2100 along the

Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) using GDP per capita, gender equality, and education as drivers (Andrijevic et al., 2019).

However, this approach has important limitations. The government effectiveness indicator is highly correlated with GDP per capita and does not fully capture the drivers of climate ambition. For instance, countries such as Australia and the United States, despite scoring high on institutional capacity, have historically maintained high per capita emissions and delayed robust mitigation efforts. This suggests that while institutional capacity may enable effective implementation once policies are adopted, it does not necessarily reflect political will or societal support for climate action. Accordingly, institutional capacity should be understood as a stylized proxy for implementation potential and regional differentiation, rather than as a predictor of actual policy outcomes.

The resulting 12 harmonized scenarios were quantified using eight global IAMs: AIM, COFFEE, GEM-E3, IMAGE, MESSAGEix, POLES, REMIND, and WITCH. In addition to institutional constraints, the scenarios include a suite of technological feasibility constraints, such as (for full details please refer to Bertram et al., 2024):

- A global cap on bioenergy use aligned with sustainability concerns (100 EJ/year)
- Regional upper bounds on geological Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) potential
- Global upper limits on the deployment of solar, wind, nuclear, and CCS technologies
- Constraints on Direct Air Capture with Carbon Storage (DACCS) and Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage (BECCS)

Scenarios were modeled under two global carbon budgets, using 2018 as the reference year:

- A 1000 GtCO₂ budget, which lies just below the 1170 GtCO₂ estimate associated with a 67% chance of limiting warming to below 2°C
- A 550 GtCO₂ budget, which falls between the 50th percentile estimate of 580 GtCO₂ and the 67th percentile estimate of 420 GtCO₂ for limiting warming to 1.5°C

The scenarios were organized into six narrative categories:

Table 1: Scenario narratives

Scenario Name	CO ₂ Budget	Carbon Price	Technology Constraints	Institutional Constraints	Enablers
1.5°C Default	550 GtCO ₂	Uniform	–	–	–
2°C Default	1000 GtCO ₂	Uniform	–	–	–
2°C Feasibility	1000 GtCO ₂	Differentiated	✓	✓	–
Below 2°C Enablers	550 GtCO ₂ or lowest feasible	Differentiated	Only CDR	✓	✓

In this report (as also in Brutschin et al. (under review)), we focus on the regional outcomes of this new feasibility-informed scenarios, assessing their implications for regional CO₂ emissions reductions, net-zero targets, and carbon budgets. We compare these to a default scenario in which all regions follow cost-optimal global IAM assumptions. This “2°C Default” scenario is based on a uniform global carbon price and a global carbon budget consistent with limiting warming to 2°C. Under these conditions, mitigation efforts are distributed relatively evenly across the three major regions (see Figure 1, Panels A and D). In this default configuration, the OECD90+ region is projected to reach net-zero CO₂ emissions around 2063, with other regions reaching net-zero closer to 2070 (Figure 1, Panel E).

When region-specific institutional and global technological feasibility constraints are introduced (Figure 1, Panel B; “2°C Feasibility” scenario), a clear shift in near-term mitigation emerges, with greater effort concentrated in the OECD90+ and China+ regions. In this scenario, the OECD90+ region is projected to reach net-zero CO₂ emissions around 2050, China+ by 2055, and the Rest of the World (RoW) by approximately 2075. The net-zero timeline for OECD90+ aligns closely with existing national climate pledges (Aleluia Reis & Tavoni, 2023; Rogelj et al., 2023), while the median net-zero year for China+ is five years earlier than its current official target.

Achieving a more ambitious climate target, as represented by the “Below 2°C Enablers” scenario, requires strengthened climate action across all regions (see Figure 1, Panels D and E). In this scenario, the OECD90+ countries would need to reduce CO₂ emissions by approximately 85% by 2040 compared to 2020 levels, with a model

range of 81–114%, and reach net-zero around 2045. This pathway implies significantly faster emission reductions by 2035 than those suggested by current near-term pledges.

For the China+ region, the scenario suggests a 78% emissions reduction by 2040 (range: 48–83%) and achieving CO₂ net-zero around 2050. The Rest of the World (RoW) would aim for a 38% reduction by 2040 (range: 33–58%) and reach net-zero around 2070.

Figure 1: Regional CO₂ emission reduction efforts compared across three key scenario narratives

Panel (A) default uniform carbon price set-up, Panel (B) institutional and other feasibility constraints are included, and (C) all constraints and enablers are included to explore the below 2°C space. The lines in Panels A-C represent the median values from scenarios across all models. For the year 2050 in the Panels A-C we indicate the CO₂ emissions reductions (%) for a given region compared to 2020. In Panel D we then contextualize the considered scenarios by comparing regional emissions reduction for 2030, 2035, 2040 and 2050 (median across all models) with uniform carbon price in 1.5°C and 2°C aligned carbon budgets. In Panel E we compare the timing of CO₂ net-zero (median across all models) for key regions across the considered scenario set. We define CO₂ net-zero as the year when CO₂ emissions in the considered regions reach levels below 500 Mt/year. For OECD+ and China+ we indicate the pledged CO₂ net-zero year. Our NDC scenario (NDC* w/t NZ) excludes the pledged net-zero year and only incorporates the implied modeled trajectory based on NDC policies up to 2022. Please note that the results for the Enablers scenarios are based solely on five models, as these were the only ones with available implementations for the “Below 2°C Enablers” scenario.

A key takeaway from these results is the critical importance of setting clear and ambitious near-term targets, not only for 2050 but also for intermediate milestones such as 2030, 2035, and 2040. As shown in Figure 1, Panel D, the implied emissions reductions under the NDC* w/t NZ scenario for the OECD90+ region fall short—particularly for the years 2035 and 2040—when compared to what would be required under the Below 2°C pathway.

This gap suggests that, although the OECD90+ region is broadly aligned with a 2050 net-zero target, current near-term policies and sectoral targets (represented by grey empty circles) may be insufficient to stay on track, especially when regional differentiation is considered.

Achieving the “Below 2°C Enablers” scenario will require not only deep domestic emissions reductions from the OECD90+ countries but also a significant scaling-up of international support to other regions, particularly the Rest of the World (RoW). Given their earlier decarbonization trajectory and stronger institutional capacity, OECD90+ countries are in a position—and arguably bear a responsibility—to provide both financial resources and technological and institutional know-how to accelerate global climate action. This includes targeted support for clean energy deployment, grid modernization, industrial decarbonization, and climate-resilient infrastructure in emerging and developing economies. Institutional capacity-building, policy coordination, and knowledge-sharing platforms will also be essential to ensure effective implementation of mitigation strategies in regions where governance or technical gaps may slow progress. Furthermore, financial transfers—through mechanisms such as climate finance—will be crucial to mobilize the scale of investment needed in lower-income countries to meet their emissions reduction goals and close the gap between current policies and the Below 2°C pathway. This highlights the interdependence of regional climate strategies and underscores the need for a more collaborative, equity-based global approach to decarbonization.

The regional differentiation in mitigation contributions identified in our analysis can also be further examined through the lens of fairness, particularly with respect to how global mitigation efforts are distributed. Such fairness considerations are often evaluated through ex-post allocations of region- or country-specific carbon budgets. These assessments are rooted in equity principles embedded in the UNFCCC and the Paris Agreement and require careful interpretation and methodological transparency (Meinshausen et al., 2015; Pelz, Ganti, Pachauri, et al., 2024).

To explore this dimension, we compare cumulative carbon dioxide emissions from fossil fuel and industry (CO₂-FFI) under three perspectives: the default 1.5°C scenario with a uniform global carbon price, the “Below 2°C Enablers” scenario with regionally differentiated carbon prices, and a selection of ‘fair’ carbon budget allocations for the 1.5°C target. Please note that the carbon budgets presented in this context are not strictly comparable. Rather, this representation is intended to illustrate the differences in implied global and regional climate mitigation strategies—within the context of the Paris Agreement goals—and their associated carbon budgets. For the ‘fair’ carbon budget allocations perspective, we consider four illustrative allocation approaches aligned to different degrees with interpretations of the principle of common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities (CBDR-RC). These include

two different base years (1990 or 2015), and two variants considering “ability to pay” or not, to adjust allocations by relative GDP per capita in purchasing power parity terms (GDP-PPP per capita). These are described in detail in other literature by co-authors and are used here only as reference benchmarks as their application requires a range of explicit value judgements and normative considerations beyond the scope of this work (Pelz, Ganti, Lamboll, et al., 2024).

Figure 2: Illustration of results from various allocation perspectives and key scenarios.

The bars represent the total cumulative CO₂ Fossil-Fuel and Industry (CO₂-FFI) emissions for each scenario and model. The percentages indicate each region's share of the total emissions within a given scenario and model. The bars under the allocation principles show emissions values based on equal per capita allocation for the indicated years as the starting point (1990 versus 2015), while the tails represent the full range of values under different allocation principles and possible calculations. Please note that we present five models here, as these were the only ones with available implementations for the “Below 2°C Enablers” scenario.

Figure 2 highlights the differences between these pathways. The “Below 2°C Enablers” scenario (in green), which incorporates differentiated regional carbon prices (based on the institutional capacity), is contrasted with the 1.5°C default scenario (in grey), based on a uniform global price. The figure shows cumulative CO₂-FFI emissions across models and allocation schemes. A key insight is that, under regionally differentiated carbon prices, the Rest of the World (RoW) accounts for nearly half of global CO₂-FFI emissions—up from roughly one-third under the default scenario. In absolute terms, the RoW’s carbon budget in these differentiated scenarios is more closely aligned with budgets calculated using a range of fairness-based allocation approaches.

Conversely, the OECD90+ region has, in many cases, already exceeded — or even entered into carbon debt relative to — its fair share of the 1.5°C carbon budget, depending on the allocation method used. To approach a more equitable outcome, the OECD90+ region would need to significantly scale up support for mitigation efforts in other regions or increase domestic deployment of Carbon Dioxide Removal (CDR) and Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) technologies to generate negative emissions.

Overall, this scenario set demonstrates that introducing regional differentiation based on institutional capacity leads to substantial shifts in implied regional mitigation burdens. However, the gap between modeled outcomes and what would be considered equitable under various equity principles remains significant. This underscores the need to complement governance- and feasibility-based scenario differentiation with additional equity-oriented dimensions in IAM frameworks — particularly to better reflect both intergenerational and intragenerational justice.

3. Net-zero Carbon Debt

Summary of insights from Pelz, S., Ganti, G., Lamboll, R., Grant, L., Smith, C., Pachauri, S., Rogelj, J., Riahi, K., Thiery, W., & Gidden, M. J. (2025). Using net-zero carbon debt to track climate overshoot responsibility. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 122(13), e2409316122. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2409316122>

Here we introduce the concept of ‘net-zero carbon debt’, a forward-looking measure of responsibility for exceeding a fair share of the remaining carbon budget at the point when a party reaches net-zero carbon emissions (Pelz et al., 2025). This concept emerges as an extension of earlier literature establishing the notion of a ‘fair share’ of a remaining carbon budget, and the comparison of such ‘fair shares’ with past emissions.

Drawing directly from the Paris Agreement’s 1.5C limit, the ‘net-zero carbon debt’ concept explicitly determines individual party’s obligations for subsequent return to 1.5C after temporary exceedance, or overshoot. This concept integrates historical emissions, projected future emissions and fair share allocations of the remaining carbon budget in a single unified measure.

Figure 3: The persistent accrual of net-zero carbon debt. Regional net-zero carbon debt is quantified by subtracting (i) past and (ii) future cumulative carbon emissions from (iii) a 'fair' allocation of the total carbon budget comprising both a remaining carbon budget (RCB) and past global carbon emissions as desired.

In their study, Pelz et al. (2025) operationalise the measure using both the IPCC's Sixth Assessment Report (WGIII) scenario ensemble as well as two new scenarios describing expected emissions trajectories under current policies and current net-zero pledges. As shown in Figure 3, the approach to quantify the net-zero carbon debt involves three components:

1. Historical carbon emissions from fossil fuels and industry (CO₂-FFI). Noting that the implications of this decision and reasoning is discussed at length in the article.
2. A fair share allocation of the total carbon budget (historical emissions plus RCB), which is illustrated using an equal cumulative per capita basis from the year 1990.
3. Projected future emissions under various mitigation scenarios.

To illustrate its application, they define a total carbon budget combining historical global fossil fuel and industrial process carbon dioxide (CO₂-FFI) emissions from 1990 onwards with an estimated remaining carbon budget (RCB) consistent with limiting global warming to 1.5°C (approximately 247 GtCO₂ starting in 2023). The choice of 1990 aligns with the first systematic scientific communication of climate change to policymakers (IPCC's first assessment). This total budget is then allocated equally per capita, aligning with the principles of common but differentiated

responsibilities and respective capabilities (CBDR-RC) qualified in the Paris Agreement and the Polluter Pays principle drawn from climate justice literature.

Figure 4: Differentiated carbon debt accrual and overshoot responsibilities under current policies and pledges. (a) Estimated median climate overshoot under the assessed scenarios (33rd-66th global mean temperature anomaly quantiles as ribbon). (b) The evolution of emissions pathways, carbon debt accrual and corresponding overshoot responsibilities, separating regions that accrue carbon debt by 2030 from those that accrue carbon debt later (see grouping in caption). This considers an equal cumulative per capita allocation of the total carbon budget from the year 1990, comprising global CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel and industrial processes (CO₂-FFI) between the years 1990-2023 and an estimated 1.5°C RCB (50% chance) from the year 2023.

By applying this framework to vetted scenarios from the IPCC’s Sixth Assessment Report (AR6) scenarios database, Pelz et al. (2025) illustrate differentiated trajectories of carbon debt accrual across regions in the most recently communicated best available science (see Figure 4). Specifically, their findings delineate three distinct regional groups based on net-zero carbon debt accrual patterns:

- Regions consistently accruing net-zero carbon debt regardless of net-zero CO₂ timing (e.g., North America, Europe, Asia-Pacific Developed, Middle East).

- Regions potentially accruing debt depending on net-zero CO₂ timing (e.g., Latin America and Caribbean, Developing Pacific).
- Regions unlikely to accrue debt this century (e.g., Sub-Saharan Africa, Southern Asia).

These illustrative distinctions underscore the normative differences in historical and future emissions responsibilities across global regions. The aim of this work is, however, not to define what is 'fair' but rather to demonstrate the value of the net-zero carbon debt measure for national and multilateral deliberations – where a desired normative position on what is a given party's fair share can be used to determine the expected net-zero carbon debt accrual and thus contribution to overshoot by the time the party expects to achieve net-zero carbon emissions. This is therefore to be understood as a bottom-up measure, or support tool, to be used independently by parties and aid their determination of highest possible domestic ambition [alongside contributions to international mitigation efforts where these fall short of avoiding net-zero carbon debt accrual.

To update the assessed scenarios to recent emissions and assess the implications under possible scenarios of the future, the authors further analyse two new policy scenarios representing current global climate ambitions, as shown in Figure 3 below:

- The CurPol (Current Policies) scenario, depicting limited climate action based on currently implemented policies, leading to a global mean temperature rise of approximately 3°C by 2100.
- The CurPledge (Current Pledges) scenario, representing full implementation of current pledges and targets, leading to a global temperature peak around 1.8°C by 2050.

Figure 5: The consumption of allocated remaining carbon budgets from the year 1990-2100 under the main allocation approach examined, visualizing the differences in debt accrual between 'earlier debtors' (left) and 'later debtors' (right), for the two scenarios.

This analysis reveals stark disparities in carbon drawdown obligations following overdraft of a region's fair share - notably highlighting how delayed mitigation actions exacerbate interregional and intergenerational inequities. Regions categorized as "early debtors," having historically high emissions, bear significant responsibility for immediate carbon drawdown efforts. Conversely, "later debtor" regions, though less historically responsible, increasingly contribute to global carbon debt under prolonged low-ambition scenarios.

Reconciling the complexity in multilateral negotiations, the authors then investigate the domestic implications of net-zero carbon debt accrual, by assessing responsibility for the increase in projected lifetime exposure to extreme heatwaves due to overshoot. Their findings demonstrate that younger generations across all regions face significantly greater exposure to extreme climate events relative to older cohorts, an inequity intensified by differentiated carbon budget exceedance responsibilities across regions. High-emitting regions impose disproportionately large climate impacts and drawdown burdens on future generations.

Figure 6: Differentiated carbon debt accrual and overshoot responsibilities under current policies and pledges. (a) Estimated median climate overshoot under the assessed scenarios (33rd-66th global mean temperature anomaly quantiles as ribbon). **(b)** The evolution of emissions pathways, carbon debt accrual and corresponding overshoot responsibilities, separating regions that accrue carbon debt by 2030 from those that accrue carbon debt later (see grouping in caption). This considers an equal cumulative per capita allocation of the total carbon budget from the year 1990, comprised of global CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel and industrial processes (CO₂-FFI) between the years 1990-2023 and an estimated 1.5°C RCB (50% chance) from the year 2023.

This work emphasizes the critical need for intensified global cooperation and ambitious mitigation policies aligned with fairness principles. Pelz et al. (2025) advocate that equitable management of carbon debt, incorporating clear sovereign quantification of regional and generational responsibilities, could inform international climate finance and policy frameworks, including the development and implementation of Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs).

Figure 7: Increased extreme heatwave exposure and carbon drawdown obligations under current policies and pledges. Increase in years of life exposed to extreme (1-in-100-year) heatwaves (primary y-axis) relative to the 1.5°C reference scenario (IMP-REN, AR6), for all cohorts born between 1960-2020 (x-axis). The shaded areas reflect the 33rd and 66th percentile across all global climate model runs and temperature response quantiles (see Methods). The annual equal per capita drawdown obligation to address regional responsibility for scenario overshoot by the year 2100 is shown on the secondary y-axis. This considers an equal cumulative per capita allocation of the total carbon budget from the year 1990, comprising global CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel and industrial processes (CO₂-FFI) between the years 1990-2023 and an estimated 1.5°C RCB (50% chance) from the year 2023.

In conclusion, the concept of net-zero carbon debt serves as a useful analytical tool for understanding and managing climate overshoot responsibilities after remaining carbon budget depletion. Its robust methodological approach offers clear pathways to equitable international climate action, guiding both regional and intergenerational obligations to limit and return global mean temperature increase to acceptable levels.

4. Ambition through justice and societal considerations

The Integrated Assessment Modeling (IAM) community is increasingly being called upon to enhance the diversity, transparency, and inclusivity of its models and practices (Clift & Kuzemko, 2024; Cointe et al., 2019). These calls reflect growing concerns over the relatively narrow set of assumptions that often underpin IAM scenarios and the limited responsiveness of many models to region-specific priorities. These critiques are particularly salient in the context of the Paris Agreement, where nationally determined actions form the foundation of global efforts, and where equity considerations are key to designing just and workable climate strategies (Dubash, 2023).

In parallel, it is critical to consider the challenges of policy implementation. Institutional capacity plays a central role in shaping how effectively countries can design, adopt, and enforce climate policies. Countries with stronger institutions often demonstrate a greater ability to manage complex regulatory environments, mobilize resources, and sustain credible long-term commitments. These capabilities can support more ambitious actions such as implementing carbon pricing, phasing out fossil fuels, or scaling up renewable energy systems. However, this framing also has limitations. Institutional indicators are often closely linked to income levels and may not fully capture the underlying drivers of climate ambition or political will. This suggests that institutional strength, while important, is not a guarantee of ambitious climate action. Rather, it should be viewed as a proxy for the potential to implement policy effectively – one that must be complemented by political leadership, societal support, and coherent national strategies.

A central finding of the work presented in section 2 is that incorporating governance and feasibility into integrated assessment models significantly reshapes regional mitigation pathways. The “2°C Feasibility” and “Below 2°C Enablers” scenarios show that considering institutional capacity would significantly shift the distribution of effort across regions. In particular, OECD90+ and China+ regions would need to take on more ambitious near-term targets under feasibility-informed scenarios, closely aligning with or even exceeding current national commitments. This adjustment highlights the importance of recognizing regional capacity constraints and policy realism when assessing mitigation burdens.

At the same time, the incorporation of differentiated regional carbon prices along institutional capacity, as in the Below 2°C Enablers scenario, brings regional emissions outcomes closer to various fairness-based budget allocations. Nevertheless, a large literature discussing fair-share comparisons across multiple burden-sharing principles reveals that the current generation of IAM scenarios, even those with differentiated assumptions, tend to under-represent equity considerations rooted in historical emissions and capacity. Here, the Rest of the World, for example, gains a larger emissions share under differentiated carbon pricing, yet many OECD90+ countries still exceed their calculated fair shares, even under the most lenient interpretations.

It is important to recognize here that justice is a multidimensional concept that extends far beyond emissions allocations and has been explored across numerous

disciplines. In the context of climate change, recent research conceptualizes Earth System justice as consisting of interregional, intergenerational, and interspecies justice perspectives (Gupta et al., 2023; Zimm et al., 2024). While IAMs cannot capture every facet of justice described here, they serve as valuable tools to examine the implications of different justice dimensions and provide quantifiable insights into how equity-related trade-offs might unfold in practice.

Illustrating one example of how to integrate interregional and intergenerational justice in future scenarios, the concept of net-zero carbon debt outlined in section 3 provides a critical innovation for reconciling global ambition with regionally grounded action. Net-zero carbon debt offers a bottom-up measure of responsibility that countries can apply using their own emissions trajectories, targets, and sectoral plans. This enables countries to assess their carbon budget exceedance and resulting drawdown obligations corresponding to a country-specific mitigation pathway. In doing so, it supports transparent, country-led deliberations about ambition, equity, and the need for international support - particularly in contexts where fairness is contested but claims of responsibility and capability must still be communicated clearly.

At the same time, incorporating net-zero carbon debt into IAM frameworks can enhance their ability to represent differentiated regional responsibilities and long-term overshoot burdens. It allows scenarios to track not only how and when a region contributes to budget exceedance, but also how much carbon dioxide it must remove in the future to return to agreed temperature limits. This enables a more granular assessment of which regions require greater near-term ambition or long-term removal capacity. Crucially, it provides a modular, interoperable fairness layer that does not alter the structure of underlying IAMs, but rather complements them - offering a tool that policymakers and researchers alike can use to evaluate whether national or collective action aligns with a just transition. By bridging globally defined temperature goals with nationally defined contributions, net-zero carbon debt provides an actionable link between fairness in principle and fairness in practice.

Taken together, these findings reinforce the need for a dual integration of feasibility and fairness considerations in global mitigation pathways. Feasibility considerations, captured through institutional capacity and other technological constraints, ensures that proposed pathways are not violating some of the core plausibility concerns. Fairness, captured through carbon debt and differentiated allocations, ensures that those pathways are aligned with climate justice principles and international equity norms. By combining these dimensions IAM scenarios could be more aligned with the Paris Agreement's dual objectives of limiting warming and achieving a just transition.

Furthermore, this integration has important implications for international cooperation mechanisms. The carbon debt framework, for example, can guide differentiated contributions to global mitigation finance, support mechanisms of cooperation under the Paris Agreement, and inform the evolution of NDCs. Similarly, feasibility-informed scenarios can help identify where capacity-building efforts and technology transfers are most urgently needed. In future work, these frameworks should be expanded to include adaptation, loss and damage, and interspecies perspectives of justice. This would further strengthen the capacity of IAMs and policy frameworks to reflect the full spectrum of fairness concerns relevant to climate governance.

A new initiative that builds on and extends these developments is the Justice Model Intercomparison Project (JustMIP), initiated under Task 5.4 of the ELEVATE project with strong linkages to other ELEVATE work packages. JustMIP responds directly to longstanding critiques about the limited representation of fairness and justice in IAMs by systematically incorporating differentiated responsibilities, development needs, and sustainability constraints into scenario design. Developed through collaboration between contributors from both Annex I and Non-Annex I countries, JustMIP offers a structured scenario matrix exploring the interaction between universal Decent Living Standards, fair effort-sharing, and planetary boundary constraints such as biodiversity and geological storage limits. It thereby enables model-based exploration of how interregional and intergenerational justice considerations shape mitigation pathways, ambition levels, and cooperation needs under the Paris Agreement.

While rooted in the ELEVATE project, JustMIP is designed as an open, community-oriented protocol. Its scenario architecture layers a series of justice dimensions - such as historical responsibility, minimum energy provisioning, and biodiversity constraints - on top of conventional mitigation targets. This approach allows researchers and policymakers to explore how different justice framings affect regional emissions trajectories, feasibility conditions, and long-term carbon removal burdens. In this way, JustMIP contributes not only to the diversification and legitimacy of IAM outputs, but also to broader efforts, within and beyond ELEVATE, to align ambitious global mitigation scenarios with considerations of regional fairness and societal acceptance.

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Annex I

Pelz, Setu; Brutschin, Elina – *Discussing the Governance of Carbon Dioxide Removal*, SBSTA Session, 5 June 2024.

Riahi, Keywan – *Austrian Contributions from the Fairness Perspective*, Klimaaktiv Talk, 10 June 2024.

Pelz, Setu – *Tracking Net-Zero Carbon Debt Analysis of Carbon Debt Following Different Pathways*, SBSTA Side Event, 11 June 2024.

Riahi, Keywan – *Session on Justice in Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs)*, Climate Solutions Summit, 11 June 2024.

Brutschin, Elina; Pachauri, Shonali – *Just Transition Scenarios*, UNEP FI Scenario Analysis and Stress Testing Working Group – Just Transition Session, 13 December 2024.

Pelz, Setu – *Just Transition Pathways of India in Global/National Context – The Relevance of Financial Transfers*, COMMITTED & ELEVATE Modelling & Stakeholder Workshop, India, 23–24 October 2024.

van Ruijven, Bas – *Advancing Justice Considerations in IAM Scenarios, A Holistic Approach to Climate-Resilient, Just Development: Translating Evidence into Action*, Official Side Event at COP29, 18 November 2024.

van Ruijven, Bas – *Addressing Regional Feasibility Concerns in the Race to Net Zero*, Presentation at COP29, EF China's LTS luncheon, 16 November 2024.

Pelz, Setu – *Normative Considerations in Integrated Assessment Modelling*, IAMC 2024 Plenary Session, November 2024.

Brutschin, Elina – *Justice Considerations and Carbon Debt*, ELEVATE Co-Creation Workshop on National and Global Net-Zero Strategies, Saudi Arabia, 23 January 2025.

Brutschin, Elina – *JustMIP*, MESSAGE Community Meeting, 20 May 2025.

Pelz, Setu – *JustMIP: Advancing Justice Considerations in IAM Scenarios*, Research Dialogue Poster and Presentation, SBSTA Bonn, 17 June 2025.

Brutschin, Elina – *Co-Creating Paris-Aligned Pathways: A Stakeholder Dialogue on Justice and Development*, V ELEVATE International Stakeholder Workshop, Bonn, 20 June 2025.

Riahi, Keywan – *Introducing JustMIP, Advancing Justice Considerations in Climate Policy – Bridging National and Global Perspectives*, SBSTA Official Side Event, 26 June 2025.

Brutschin, Elina – *Normative Considerations in Global IAMs*, PRISMA Summer School, 9 July 2025.

Pelz, Setu – *Exploring Transformation Pathways for Managing Climate Overshoot Responsibility*, Scenarios Forum, 23 July 2025.

Pelz, Setu – *Equity in CMIP7 scenarios and beyond*, Scenarios Forum, 23 July 2025.